

Appendices

A. Session Demo (Illustration of session 1)

A.1 Preparation of the elicitation interview

Context: Business process analysts prepare the interview canvas that will guide the semi-structured discussion conducted by the conversational agent. They have the option of adding an “expected output” if they want the conversational agent to specifically verify that domain experts mention these elements (See B.1 Socialization).

Tailor Questions and Expected Outputs

Enter Questions

Question 1

Qui sont les personnes responsables de la facturation ?

Question 2

Quels sont les types de ventes ou achats qui sont facturés ? Veuillez compléter cette liste si nécessaire : Certificats Verts, Garantie d'Origine & Proof of Sustainability (PoS), gaz, matière agricole

Question 3

Quels sont les types de factures qui existent?

Question 4

Le processus de facturation varie-t-il selon le type de vente?

Question 5

Quels sont les déclencheurs possibles pour générer une facture pour chaque type de vente (événement spécifique, fréquence fixée) ?"

Enter Expected Outputs

Expected Output 1

Actors

Expected Output 2

Invoices types

Expected Output 3

Types & format of invoices

Expected Output 4

Expected Output 5

...

A.2 Socialization: Elicitation session

Context: The domain expert receives a link and login credentials to connect to a session guided by a conversational agent. They can provide information in writing or verbally by answering the conversational agent's questions. The domain expert can skip the question by using pre-designed answers if they deem it useful.

Choose Input Mode

Writing

Session in progress...

 Il y a t-il une personne référente pour valider les informations avant la génération de la facture? Est ce que cette validation a toujours lieu? Dans la négative, quels sont les critères qui permettent de définir qu'une validation doit avoir lieu?

 oui je valide le format de la facture et les directeurs concernées les informations et données de la facture

 Qui est responsable de la génération des factures ?

 Moi, je demande à mon équipe de générer la facture et je supervise ce qu'ils ont générés puis c'est validé par le directeur cnoerné

 Selon les types de ventes : qui sont les destinataires des factures ?

 les agriculteurs ou autres clients (énergie,...)

"I don't know" "Question not relevant or already answered" "You should ask to someone else" Other **Generate Model**

Please, provide a lot of process insights

A.2 Externalization: Formalization of process knowledge

Context: At the end of the session, business process analysts can view the results generated by the multi-agent system. In particular, they can download the generated .bpmn file.

Process Description

BPMN model

This section provides a high level description of the process flow...

The process begins with each department providing necessary billing information. The responsibility for overseeing the billing process lies with a supervisor, under whom different departments contribute their respective data. Margaux is in charge of invoicing, while Matthieu handles the transition from Excel to Odoo.

Factures include various types such as agricultural services, energy, and environmental certificates. Initially, they are created using Excel, but there's a shift towards using Odoo, especially for expense reports already transitioned. Each month, particularly for agricultural invoices, data is compiled in the initial days via a pivot table developed by agronomists. These and other invoices are generated as required, based on contracts.

The generated invoices require validation. Supervisors and pertinent directors examine the invoice format and content. The financial department uses macros to manage elements like billing numbers and ensures accuracy, particularly during periods of high activity like December.

Destinataires of invoices include customers like farmers or energy clients, identified through an internal database maintained by agronomists and accessible through both Excel and Odoo. The database ensures the precision of recipient information, and plans are in place to exclusively use Odoo in the future.

Invoices are primarily sent via email without a specific timeline, aiming for promptness particularly at the beginning of each month. The responsibility for sending resides with the supervisor and Margaux. Although there is no designated individual for deadline compliance, any delay has mechanisms for resolution.

Invoices are archived using Cloud Demat and internally managed, with the financial team ensuring oversight. Payment follow-up is conducted by the supervisor who uses Cloud Demat's virtual recognition to integrate billing information. Reconciliation occurs every two months using data exports from BOB, tackling issues like missing invoices by sourcing duplicates, often assisted by Margaux.

In case of unpaid invoices, reminders are sent post-investigation. No standardized process exists for these scenarios, but effective communications and reconciliations with other departments are crucial in addressing discrepancies. Reconciliation after fiscal closures typically concludes within five to six months.

Process Structured Documentation

This section provides a detailed description of the documented process...

Process Description

1. Actors • Process Owner: Responsable de la facturation • Département financier • Agronomes • Directeurs de département • Équipe de facturation (y compris Margaux) • Fiduciaire • Matthieu [redacted] (en charge de la transition vers Odoo)
2. Tasks • Collecte des informations de facturation auprès des différents départements • Mise à jour et maintenance de la base de données interne (Excel et Odoo) • Génération de la facture par l'équipe de facturation • Validation du format des factures par le responsable et par les directeurs concernés • Attribution des numéros de facturation et vérification des montants • Transmission des factures aux destinataires via email • Intégration des informations de facturation dans le système comptable (Cloud Demat) • Suivi des paiements et réconciliation des factures et paiements • Gestion des écarts et demande de duplicata en cas de facture ou ticket manquant
3. Events • Start Event: Déclenchement du processus par la réception de données de facturation (par exemple, début du mois, contrats ponctuels ou événements spécifiques) • Intermediate Event: Validation intermédiaire des informations par les directeurs et vérification des données dans la base interne • Intermediate Event: Notification des paiements reçus et détection d'événements de rappel en cas de paiement manquant • End Event: Facture validée, envoyée au client et intégrée dans Cloud Demat • End Event alterné: Processus de réconciliation complété et écarts traités
4. Gateways • Gateways de décision lors de la validation de la facture (si la facture est conforme : poursuivre le processus, sinon renvoyer pour correction) • Gateways décisionnelles pour le déclenchement du processus de réconciliation (en fonction de la présence ou non de factures ou tickets manquants) • Gateways de vérification de la transition Excel vers Odoo (étapes prévues par Matthieu [redacted] et diffusion de l'information)
5. Systems and Supporting Files/Documents • Systèmes et outils
 - Excel (support existant pour la création et le suivi des factures)
 - Odoo (système cible pour les modèles de ventes et bordereaux, base de données centralisée)
 - Cloud Demat (système comptable pour l'intégration des informations de facturation)
 - Export de BOB (outil utilisé pour la réconciliation des paiements) • Documents et fichiers de support
 - Tableaux de facturation compilés par les agronomes (avec macro pour création des factures)
 - Modèles de factures (formats spécifiques pour factures d'achats, de ventes, bordereaux et notes de frais)
 - Base de données clients et partenaires (mise à jour par les agronomes et sauvegardée dans Odoo et Excel)
 - Registre des numéros de facturation et historique de suivi (dans Cloud Demat et drive géré par l'équipe DAF)

Context: .bpmn graphic generated by the tool following session 1. The layout has been modified to improve the clarity of the illustration in .png format. (Model presented in the paper and in supplementary materials (in .bpmn format)).

Appendix

Conversation with Domain Experts

This section provides a detailed description of the documented process...

Bonjour, êtes-vous prêt à modéliser votre processus ? 🙋

-oui

-Quelles sont les principales difficultés rencontrées dans le processus de facturation actuel ?

Y a-t-il des formations ou des supports disponibles pour les employés impliqués dans le processus de facturation ?

-Plusieurs personnes doivent donner des infos pour la facturation et parfois on a un souci de communication et également on a pour le moment uniquement un support excel mais on aimerait passer sur Odoo pour les modèles de ventes et bordereaux.

-Comment envisagez-vous la transition d'Excel vers Odoo pour la facturation, et quelles étapes prévoyez-vous pour assurer une adoption réussie ?

Quels mécanismes de communication pourraient être mis en place pour améliorer le partage d'informations entre les différentes personnes impliquées dans le processus de facturation ?

-je ne peux répondre à cette question c'est Matthieu qui s'en occupe avec odoo

-1. Comment Matthieu envisage-t-il la transition d'Excel vers Odoo pour la facturation, et quelles étapes prévoit-il pour assurer une adoption réussie ? 2. Quels mécanismes de communication pourraient être mis en place pour améliorer le partage d'informations entre les différentes personnes impliquées dans le processus de facturation ?

-Skip : Je ne sais pas

-Qui sont les personnes responsables de la facturation ?

-Je suis responsable, chaque département donne les infos de facturations, Margaux facture et moi je supervise

-Quels sont les types de ventes ou achats qui sont facturés ? Veuillez compléter cette liste si nécessaire : Certificats Verts, Garantie d'Origine & Proof of Sustainability (PoS), gaz, matière agricole

-en plus de la liste, on peut ajouter ETS, prestation de service agricole, refacturation en tout genre, digestat,...

-Quels sont les types de factures qui existent?

...

B. Design choices

Here is a brief description of the design choices that could influence our results.

B.1 Socialization

This section outlines the complete set of actions undertaken by the agents in the continuous supervision of the interaction between the domain expert and the conversational agent responsible for knowledge elicitation (i.e., Elicitor).

Fig. 6 Conversation monitoring using semi-guided interviews. Inspired by Hu et al. (2024)

Willingness or Ability Check:

The first test aims to assess the willingness or ability of the domain expert to respond to a given question. If the agent determines that the user is either unwilling or unable to provide an answer, it proceeds to the next question without generating a follow-up, in order to preserve the domain expert's user experience. In the two images below, we can observe that the domain expert expresses—in two different ways—that they do not have an answer to the questions selected by the tool. In such cases, as indicated by the code trace logs (see below), the test returns a positive result, meaning that no follow-up question should be generated.

Provide insights

- How the process starts ? This question focuses on the events or conditions that initiate the process.
- When I receive an order from the customer. I can receive it either by mail or phone.
- What information do you need to collect from the customer when they place an order?
How do you confirm the order with the customer?
- I'm not the seller, you should ask to him
- Describe the different activities of your process. For each activities, mention the actor responsible for that

Provide insights

- How do you plan to start monitoring the delivery company's adherence to the SLA in the future?
What steps could you take to systematically gather and analyze customer feedback to improve your process?
- I don't know
- What marks the completion of the process? Describe how the process can end.
- The process is completed when the pizza is deliver to the customer. Our very final point is that the customer finishes eating the pizza.
- The interview is now over. Would you like to add anything? If not, press "Stop" to end the interview.

```
-----
IDK: (false = not detected) True
[]
```

Prompt:

```
def checkIDK(question, answer):
    """This function will check if the end-users what to express that he/she does not
    know about the topic asked. You Should ask to someone esle !"""
    client = OpenAI()
    response = client.chat.completions.create(
        messages= st.session_state["messages"][-50:] + [
            {"role": "user", "content": " Here is the question asked: " + str(question) +
            "\n. Here is the answer to the question: " + str(answer) + "."},
            {"role": "user", "content": " Check if the answer wants to express that the
            interviewed people want to express that they don't know"},
            {"role": "user", "content": " Some clue should be expression such as: 'i don't
            know', 'ask to another person', 'i'm not responsible of that',"
            " 'i'm not sure', 'nothing more to say', 'Not relevant', 'not my scope', 'not
            defined'..."},
            {"role": "user", "content": " if you diagnosed this in the answer, the output
            must be '1', else the output must contain '0'"}],
        max_tokens=None, n=1, stop=None, temperature=0, model= model)
    IDK = False
    idk_response = response.choices[0].message.content
    if "1" in idk_response:
        IDK = True
    return IDK
```

Expected output follow-up:

The second test is designed to emphasize the key elements, from the analyst’s perspective, that are expected during information gathering (i.e., expected outputs). This test focuses on assessing whether these essential elements are present in the domain expert’s response. The images below illustrate a case in which the details provided by the domain expert are insufficient.

In this example, the threshold is set at 4 out of 10. When the score falls below this threshold, a follow-up question is automatically generated.


```
-----
IDK: (false = not detected) False
The answer should mention Process Trigger Condition and light Description of how the process starts
check with expected outputs
Expected output check score (below 4 on ten means not enough details provided):0
```

Prompt:

```
def check_expected(expected, question, prompt):
    """
    This function checks if the answer provides sufficient information about the
    expected output element.
    """
    client = OpenAI()
    response = client.chat.completions.create(
        messages=st.session_state["messages"][-50:] + [
            {"role": "user", "content": f"Here is the answer to a question. \n
            Question: {question} \n Answer: {prompt}. \n\n Can you check if the answer provides
            information about these elements: {expected}?"},
            {"role": "user", "content": "Give a score from 1 to 10. Provide a
            bad score (less than 5) if there is missing elements or if the quality of the answer
            is really poor"},
            {"role": "user", "content": "The answer must only contain the score,
            no other comments"},
            {"role": "user", "content": f"Appendix \n \n Context of the company
            :\n {st.session_state["Context"]} " }
        ],
        max_tokens=1, n=1, stop=None, temperature=0, model=model)
    response_content = response.choices[0].message.content
    try:
        score = int(''.join(filter(str.isdigit, response_content)))
    except ValueError:
        score = 0
```

```

print ("Expected output check score (Below threshold on ten means not enough
details concerning expected outputs):" + str(score))
return score

```

If follow-up needed:

```

def GenFollowUp(question, prompt, Expected_Outputs):
    client = OpenAI()
    questions = " "
    for e in st.session_state["CANVA"]["Questions"]:
        questions += "\n" + str(e)
    response = client.chat.completions.create(
        messages= st.session_state["messages"][-50:] + [
            {"role": "assistant", "content": " Here is the question asked: "
+ str(question)},
            {"role": "user", "content": "Here is the answer to the question:
" + str(prompt) + ". \n The answer does not provide sufficient information about some
of these elements: " + str (Expected_Outputs) + ". Please, generate a follow-up
question in order to get insights about the elements that are not discussed. Ask a
process oriented question understandable for novice stakeholders."},
            {"role": "user", "content": "The output must be the questions
without any comments!"},
            {"role": "user", "content": "One question in the output, no
more."},
            {"role": "user", "content": f"\n Appendix \n \n Context of the
company :\n {st.session_state["Context"]} "},
            {"role": "user", "content": f"\n \n Attention: here are the
questions that must not be asked because they are already planned :\n
{st.session_state["CANVA"]}. Do not repeat them in the output and do not ask the same
question twice (see conversation history and question scheduled). "}],
        max_tokens=None, n=1, stop=None, temperature=0.5, model= model)
    Question = response.choices[0].message.content
    return Question

```

Standard follow-up:

When no expected outputs are defined or when the information provided sufficiently addresses the targeted points, we proceed to a different type of test. This test evaluates the semantic quality and coherence of the user's response within the context of the ongoing conversation. Similar to the previous test, a score ranging from 1 to 10 is returned. If the score exceeds the predefined threshold (set to 4 in our case), the information is considered satisfactory (*info ok* = 0). Otherwise, a follow-up question is generated to clarify the inconsistencies (*info ko* = 1).


```

-----
IDK: (false = not detected) False
None
check with provided information
response: 1
Check info score: (0 = infos ok, 1 = info ko ) 1

```

No Follow-up:

In the final case, the information collected is deemed sufficient, and no follow-up question is generated.

```

-----
IDK: (false = not detected) False
None
check with provided information
response: 0
Check info score: (0 = infos ok, 1 = info ko ) 0

```

Prompt:

```

def checkInfo(question, prompt):
    client = OpenAI()
    response = client.chat.completions.create(
        messages= st.session_state["messages"][-50:] + [
            {"role": "assistant", "content": f"Question: {question}"},
            {"role": "user", "content": f"Answer: {prompt}"},
            {"role": "user", "content": "Evaluate the answer based on two criteria: (1)
Relevance: If the answer is logical and appropriate given the question, it is relevant.
(2) Completeness: If the answer fully addresses the question without missing key
information, it is complete. Taking into account these two criteria, provide a score
from 0 to 10, where 0 means the answer is not relevant or complete at all, and 10
means the answer is completely relevant and complete."},
            {"role": "user", "content": f"Output must only contain the score, only digits,
no other comments."},
        ],
        max_tokens=1, n=1, stop=None, temperature=0, model=model )

    response = response.choices[0].message.content
    try:
        # Assume the score is provided as a number in the response
        score = int(''.join(filter(str.isdigit, response)))

```

```

except ValueError:
    score = 10 # Default to 0 if no valid score is found

if score <=6 :
    questions = " "
    for e in st.session_state["CANVA"]["Questions"]:
        questions += "\n" + str(e)
    response = client.chat.completions.create(
        messages= st.session_state["messages"][-50:] + [
+ str(question) },
        {"role": "assistant", "content": " Here is the question asked: "
+ str(prompt)},
        {"role": "system", "content":"It seems that the answer doesn't
provide all required information, generate a follow up question or reformulate the
questions. Output must be only the question without any other comments."},
        {"role": "user", "content":"No more than 1 question in the
output"},
        {"role": "user", "content": f"Appendix \n \n Context of the company
:\n {st.session_state["Context"]} "},
        {"role": "user", "content": f"\n \n Attention: here are the
questions that must not be asked because they are already planned :\n
{st.session_state["CANVA"]}. Do not repeat them in the output and do not ask the same
question twice (see conversation history and question scheduled). "}],
        max_tokens=None,
        n=1,
        stop=None,
        temperature=0,
        model= model
    )
    TokenCounter(response)
    response = response.choices[0].message.content

    st.session_state["CANVA"]["Questions"].insert(0, response)
    st.session_state["CANVA"]["Expected Outputs"].insert(0, "None")

print ("Check info score: (10 = infos ok, 0 = info ko ) " + str(score))

```



```

131         "type": "array",
132         "items": {
133             "type": "object",
134             "required": ["Event Name", "Event Type"],
135             "properties": {
136                 "Event Name": {"type": "string"},
137                 "Event Type": {
138                     "enum": ["Message", "Timer", "Start", "Finish"],
139                     "type": "string"},
140                 "Gateway Path": {"type": "string"},
141                 "description": (
142                     "Directly specify events within the event gateway"),
143                 "Previous Gateway Path": {
144                     "type": "string",
145                     "description": "Path leading to the current gateway"},
146                 "additionalProperties": False,
147                 "additionalProperties": False,
148                 "additionalProperties": False,
149             }
150         }
151     }
152     json_rep = json.loads(response.choices[0].message.content)
153     print("json_rep: " + str(json_rep))

```

Concretely, the conversation history is first summarized by an agent using a prompt specifically designed to retain key elements in the summary. This summarized knowledge is then structured using the query illustrated above. Finally, an algorithm integrates the structured content into XML tags following the .bpmn file format. In a subsequent step, the *bpmndi* tags are also generated algorithmically.

C. Large Language Models

Models used and associated functions are detailed in (Schinckus et al. 2026). Here is the table summarizing agents' functions.

Agents	Functions	Model	Requirements
Preparator	Generate and answer process technical questions	<i>gpt-4o</i>	R6–R8
	Generate and suggest process questions	<i>gpt-4o</i>	R6–R7
	Generate and answer process technical questions (RAG)	<i>LlamaIndex</i>	R6–R8
	Generate and suggest process questions (RAG)	<i>LlamaIndex</i>	R6–R7
Interviewer	Transform text to audio	<i>whisper-1, tts-1</i>	(R9)–R14
	Transform speech to text	<i>gpt-3.5-turbo</i>	(R9)–R15
	Summarize the process flow	<i>gpt-4o</i>	R16–R19
	Mermaid flow chart creation	<i>gpt-4o</i>	R19
Elicitor	Checking user willingness or ability to answer	<i>gpt-4o</i>	R10–R13
	Checking quality (expected outputs)	<i>gpt-4o</i>	R10–R13
	Checking quality	<i>gpt-4o</i>	R10–R13
	Generate specific (expected outputs) follow-up questions	<i>gpt-4o</i>	R10–R13
	Generate generic follow-up questions	<i>gpt-4o</i>	R10–R13
Modeler	Generate process schema (enforced outputs)	<i>gpt-4o</i>	R18
	Generate process technical documentation	<i>gpt-4o</i>	R16–R19

Table. Summary of LLM-based agents supporting PKAI and their main functions from (Schinckus et al. 2026).

D. Challenges Definition

Triangulation

Through a triangulated analysis of computational logs, domain experts' feedback, and process analysts' evaluations of the results of process discovery sessions, this paper positions the performance of an LLM-based approach against industry requirements.

Computational logs : Conversation history, defined questions (from analysts), follow-up questions, elicitation times, session outputs (process model and process documentation).

Stakeholders qualitative data:

Company data: size, department, project scope description.

Domain experts data: profile, age, current position, elicitation experience, domain expertise, post session interviews (focusing on LLM-based elicitation and comparison with traditional elicitation).

Process Analysts data: profile, age, current position, process experience, observations, post-session interviews (focusing on computational logs and session output analysis).

(from paper) Figure 2. Data collected through a multi-case study standardized approach.

The objective of this study is to draw on these three data sources to highlight the challenges inherent in the use of LLMs for the semi-automated replication of the knowledge acquisition process. The authors synthesize and aggregate the various conclusions observed across these data sources. To refine, mitigate, or corroborate these conclusions, we systematically rely on multiple data sources (triangulation) to support each identified challenge. In the section below, we present the multiple data sources associated with each high-level challenge described.

Results

Results		Sources	
SC	Socialization challenges: <i>Conversational agents need to be tailored to...</i>		
SC1	Adapt guidance, stimulation, and monitoring according to domain experts' elicitation behaviors	"... the domain expert can either provide long, detailed answers..."	M7
		"... and rarely skip questions ..."	M2
		"... can produce short responses..."	M7
		"... frequently ignoring questions, and being primarily motivated by faster task completion..."	M2, M3

		<p>"...the domain expert can adopt a descriptive point of view..."</p> <p>"... discussing a meta-level stance, distinguishing between formalized and ad hoc practices, integrating contextual elements, and reflecting team coordination..."</p> <p>"... the domain expert filters questions through a self-referential lens, providing little insight into collective aspects..."</p> <p>"... Some domain experts demonstrate accurate question interpretation, structure, and contextualize their descriptions, whereas others struggle to articulate relevant information, often omitting contextual and process insights..."</p> <p>"... Confident domain experts deliver concise and streamlined responses aligned with their own interpretation of the questions..."</p> <p>"... Others are more hesitant, being uncertain regarding their contributions, offering tentative or multi-hypothesis answers..."</p>	<p>M4</p> <p>M6 + Process analysts' interviews based on conversation logs analysis.</p> <p>M4, M5 + Process analysts' interviews based on conversation logs analysis.</p> <p>M14 + Process analysts' interviews based on conversation logs analysis + Domain experts' interviews</p> <p>M7, M10 + Process analysts' interviews based on conversation logs analysis + Domain experts' interviews</p> <p>M3 + Process analysts' interviews based on conversation logs analysis + Domain experts' interviews</p>
		<p>"... we have not found clear evidence showing a dependency between behavioral types and final output..."</p>	<p>Author's statement based on process analysts' interviews based on conversation logs and session output analysis + domain experts' interviews (triangulation of qualitative analysis).</p>
SC2	Monitor the autonomy granted to domain experts	<p>"...when delegating the elicitation task to domain experts gives them discretion to judge the relevance of questions and the level of detail in their responses, which affects the quality of the knowledge elicited..."</p> <p>"... domain experts skipped 5 questions per session, because they perceived them as irrelevant, redundant, or beyond their scope of responsibility. However, many of these skipped questions (61%) were formulated by process analysts and intended to clarify essential aspects of the process..."</p>	<p>Process analysts' interviews based on conversation logs</p> <p>M2 + Process analysts' interviews based on conversation logs</p>
SC3, SC4, SC5	Conversation guidance	<p>"... On average, 9.3 follow-up questions per conversation are generated (i.e. 31% of the questions). However, these follow-up questions are not always aligned with the analysts' expectations nor always adapted to the domain experts' requirements..."</p>	<p>M1 + Process analysts' interviews based on conversation logs</p>

SC3	Recontextualize the discussion according to the topics and analytical objectives	<p>“Analysts note the dialogue’s inconsistent flow, abrupt topic shifts, and missing contextual guidance. Analysts highlight that early phases should emphasize high-level scoping, while later phases should focus on detailed aspects of process execution. This lack of structure compelled domain experts to infer the intended meaning of questions, leading to confusion and redundant explanations...”</p>	Process analysts' interviews based on conversation logs
		<p>“... Analysts report that the conversational agent could concatenate several questions on different topics, repeat previously answered ones, or insist on irrelevant aspects. In general, domain experts confirm that the lack of contextual reminders regarding the overall objective and the current state of information collected made it harder for them to situate their responses within the right analytical frame...”</p>	Process analysts' interviews based on conversation logs
SC4	Formulate specific questions presented unambiguously and pedagogically	<p>“... Missing didactic clarity and pedagogical guidance undermines the domain expert's elicitation experience and prevents the effective delegation of autonomy, for instance, when domain experts request reformulations that are often minimal and provide little pedagogical or illustrative clarification...”</p>	Process analysts' interviews based on conversation logs + Domain experts' interviews
		<p>“...While several domain experts consider our proposal easy to use, motivation decreases as the number of unclear and unspecific questions increases. When faced with long elicitation sessions, participants tend to provide shorter, less detailed answers or to disengage. For example, domain experts’ messages are longer in the first half of the session (18.2 words on average) than in the second half (13.4 words) ...”</p>	M3, M7, M9
		<p>“...This effect becomes more pronounced when the generated follow-up prompts are perceived as irrelevant or when the agent fails to integrate previously provided information...”</p>	M1, M2, M7 + Domain experts' interviews
SC5	Foster the provision of detailed, structured, and contextually informed explanations regarding exceptional process flows occurrences	<p>“Process analysts point that the conversational agent misses opportunities to prompt the domain expert to elaborate further on exceptional flows context, conditions and occurrences”</p>	M5 + Process analysts' interviews based on conversation logs
		<p>“...less frequent flows, or implicit activities that often represent crucial elements of the process. For instance, when domain experts mentioned that “some cases are handled differently,” the agent rarely pursued these leads. Consequently, these informal or exceptional practices remain tacit and unformalized...”</p>	M5

SC6, SC7, SC8	The lack of adaptive and active stimulation during the conversation	“...Other limitations concerned the lack of adaptive and active stimulation during the conversation. In general, the conversational agent did not sufficiently encourage experts to elaborate on their responses. Domain experts contributed on average only 41.7% of the total word count during sessions. This imbalance supports analysts’ assertions that LLM-based conversational agents struggle to stimulate domain experts to share detailed, complete, or exception-related knowledge autonomously.”	M7, M8 + Process analysts’ interviews based on conversation logs
SC6	Foster the elicitation of tacit and fine-grained knowledge	“... Only 11 sessions show signs of detachment from the defined procedure and depict unformalized activities. The conversations showed a consistent absence of discussion about unformalized parts of the flow. This suggests a potential gap between the proposed process model and the actual execution of the analyzed process. This lack of stimulation is also evident when exploring unexpected situations, as only 5 sessions address unexpected scenarios...”	M5, M6
SC7	Encourage domain experts in clarifying and validating the dynamics and temporality of the flow	“... Analysts highlight insufficient exploration of temporal aspects such as task interdependencies, flow triggers, and termination conditions which are critical for understanding the dynamic nature of processes. This results in difficulties to distinguish parallel and sequential flows...”	M12 + Process analysts’ interviews based on conversation logs
		“... Although some questions were relevant, several answers remain overly high-level, omitting key details like activity sequencing, and analysts note insufficient follow-up from conversational agents, leading to mixed procedural and exceptional cases presented without clear temporal or logical order...”	M14 + Process analysts’ interviews based on conversation logs
SC8	Encourage domain experts in clarifying and validating governance mechanisms	“... analysts point out a lack of stimulation to clarify the governance mechanisms such as relationships between actors and their assigned activities, as well as the systems used to carry out these activities. When tasks appeared to overlap between individuals or teams, the lack of clarification led to potential biases or inconsistencies. For instance, when domain experts replied with “Jérôme manages this part” or “we are all responsible,” the conversational agent did not prompt follow-up clarification about specific organizational role involved. Such omissions hindered the ability to map actors accurately and identify accountability structures within the process...”	M11, M14 + Process analysts’ interviews based on conversation logs
EC	Externalization challenges: <i>Modeler agents need to be tailored to...</i>		
EC1	Abstract consistently	“Analysts emphasized limited capabilities of LLMs to abstract complex process information”	Process analysts’ interviews based on conversation logs and

	complex process information		generated process models
		"... Process models often appeared overly complex relative to the actual amount of semantic information reliable provided..."	M11-14, M15 + Process analysts' interviews based on generated process models
		"Analysts indicate that LLM-based modeling systems successfully capture general process narratives and can transform them into high-level syntactically correct diagrams but by doing some abstraction hypotheses that oversimplify the actual situation. More complex or nuanced information is typically omitted during model generation (A: the actual triggering conditions are temporal, monthly or otherwise, depending on the contracts, and not linked to data reception)."	Process analysts' interviews based on conversation logs and generated process models
		"... Session logs indicate that the number of externalized process elements tends to stabilize or even decline once the session exceeds approximately 3,500 words..."	M8, M11-13
EC2	Formalize and document exclusively verified and factual information	"...beyond granularity inconsistencies, analysts point out that models do not provide a reliable representation of the actual process flow. Information abstraction can generate hallucinated elements, such as nonexistent system integrations, invented activities, or extrapolated details..."	M14 + Process analysts' interviews based on conversation logs and generated process models
		"... This leads to the creation of scenarios or flows not described during elicitation. Moreover, when discussions focus exclusively on exceptional flows, the model may also remove implicit frequent flows, further distorting the overall process logic. For process analysts, this represents a new layer of ambiguity that necessitates systematic verification..."	M5, M6, M14 + Process analysts' interviews based on conversation logs and generated process models
EC3	Ensure uniform granularity within the same process flow	"...LLMs alternate between detailed depictions of isolated cases and generic representations, producing uneven levels of abstraction within a model (C: description of procedural activities). Some process activities are described with extensive operational detail while others are omitted, leading to conceptual imbalance and interpretative ambiguities..."	Process analysts' interviews based on conversation logs and generated process models
		"Models also lack structure as activities belonging to distinct but related workflows can be merged into a monolithic representation..."	M15 + Process analysts' interviews based on conversation logs and generated process models

EC4	Ensure a coherent integration of temporal information and logical flow conditions	“... Analysts highlight insufficient integration of temporal and conditional flow logic...”	M12, M14 + Process analysts' interviews based on conversation logs and generated process models
		“Even when domain experts describe the temporality, between concurrent or sequential, and ongoing or background activities”	Process analysts' interviews based on conversation logs and generated process models
		“... Specifically, timer events are either omitted or inconsistently assigned. Certain intermediate events are introduced without semantical justification, creating confusion (F). Decision points are sometimes misplaced or disconnected from preceding activities. Periodicities such as annual, monthly, and daily flows are neglected during abstraction...”	M15 + Process analysts' interviews based on conversation logs and generated process models
EC5	Enhance the specificity, precision, and expressiveness of process elements labels	“...The semantic clarity of labeling needs to be improved as process models do not contain specific and accurate labels to enable analysts for an unambiguous reading...”	M15 + Process analysts' interviews based on conversation logs and generated process models
		“... Activity names reflect colloquial rather than technical language (G: “Collecting billing information”). This reduces the expressiveness and pragmatism of the model. Some branching options were labeled too generically to convey meaningful process information (H). Systems also fail to clarify domain-specific jargon, creating interpretability gaps between experts and analysts...”	Process analysts' interviews based on generated process models
EC6	Ensure the consistent and correct application of BPMN syntax and notation	“Actors are sometimes represented in a group manner. A general team rather than the specific roles can be assigned (I). Actors are sometimes conflated with systems...”	M11 + Process analysts' interviews based on generated process models
		“...Actors can be represented by individual names rather than their associated roles (J). Finally, no distinction is made between external and internal actors (K)...”	M11, M15 + Process analysts' interviews based on generated process models
		“...Data objects, databases, or files, are overused. These elements are systematically linked to activities related to a system, but without involving a concrete operation or producing a real output (L). This affects the comprehensibility of the model by implying operations that are not performed...”	Authors + Process analysts' interviews based on generated process models

		<p>“... The types of activities are often specified, but some assumptions are not consistent with the process descriptions given, nor aligned with reality. Analysts highlight inconsistencies between the conversation content and the task types assigned (M: a manual task for user task) ...”</p>	<p>M13, M15 + Process analysts' interviews based on generated process models</p>
		<p>“... Events are not explicitly linked to triggering conditions. These conditions are often insufficiently formalized, preventing analysts from accurately identifying the circumstances under which a flow begins or ends (N or A).”</p>	<p>Authors + Process analysts' interviews based on generated process models</p>
		<p>“...events and gateway types are frequently intertwined. For instance, parallel gateways and exclusive gateways (O: The invoice and discrepancy correction flow runs in parallel and operates on a different temporality) or event-based and parallel gateways are confused...”</p>	<p>M12 + Process analysts' interviews based on generated process models</p>
EC7	Adhere to and comply with established best practice guidelines for modeling	<p>“...Repeated deviations from established best-practice guidelines for process modeling are observed. Models show that, on average 3 (out of 7) guidelines from (Mendling et al., 2010) are not applied ...”</p>	<p>M15 + Authors based on 7PMG</p>
		<p>“...We mainly observe a lack of conciseness, accompanied by the inclusion of superficial elements (62% of models, L or Q)...”</p>	<p>M15 + Authors based on 7PMG (G1, see Notebook 3.2)</p>
		<p>“...There is also a notable lack of structure (46% of process models), multiple routing paths per element (13% models, P), and multiple end events not connected to the main flow, even though they semantically target the same end conditions (33% models)...”</p>	<p>M15 + Authors based on 7PMG (G4, G2, G3, see Notebook 3.2)</p>